

Best Co-approximation and Best Simultaneous Co-approximation in Fuzzy Normed Spaces

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Abstract : The main purpose of this paper is to consider the t-best co-approximation and t-best simultaneous co-approximation in fuzzy normed spaces. We develop the theory of t-best co-approximation and t-best simultaneous co-approximation in quotient spaces. This new concept is employed us to improve various characterisations of t-co-proximinal and t-co-Chebyshev sets.

Keywords : fuzzy best co-approximation, fuzzy quotient spaces, proximality, Chebyshevity, best simultaneous co-approximation

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014